

Students Personality Development Paradigm: Public versus Private

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Abstract

This study is designed to compare the personality development of students at public and private schools of Punjab, Pakistan. The research study was quantitative in nature and survey was conducted to collect data. The researchers developed two questionnaires related to imparting knowledge and parameters of personality development; both questionnaires were piloted and validated before data collection. The maximum measures of imparting knowledge of personality development were best conducted in public schools as compared to private schools whereas, some measures better in private schools as compared to public schools. The parameters of personality development such as self-esteem, body language, creative problem solving, conflict and stress management, decision making skills, character building, teamwork, respect religion diversity, good manners and etiquettes, participation in group discussion, motivation, leadership qualities and respect cultural diversity are well developed in students learning in public schools as compared to students learning in private schools. The parameters of personality development like discipline, time management, speaking skills, intellectual skills, confidence, and attitude are best developed in students of private schools as compared to students of public schools

Keywords: *personality development, public schools, self-esteem, leadership qualities, etiquettes, intellectual skills.*

Introduction

According to Shukla (2014), personality is the “characteristics which determine the unique adjustment individuals make to the environment including thoughts, feelings and behaviours which distinguish individuals from others” The term personalization is the “schooling that emphasizes the needs of students as individual human beings and to personalize learning, teacher must be able to adapt to students particular interests and style” the schools tried to accomplish personalization by the use of different techniques and procedures like small classes, advisory systems, independent study, and parent teacher meetings.

Schools promote effective learning to ensure the personality development of students. The quality of personality development of students is the high time issue because these are the future of our country. The educational institution generally known as school is the second home of the students. The students live and consume five to six hours in the school. School is the place to shape the well-being of students. The development of personality not only depends on parents but also in the school environment. The schools established criteria to improve personality development. The school administration makes the students to face the challenges of the competitive world. The child in the school not only learns basic information like reading, writing, and arithmetic but also seeks a lot of information about the world — the different things like change in behaviour, confidence, discipline, and respect developed in the students which are essentials for personality development. The children seek good manners and etiquettes, speaking and intellectual skills in the schools. The education creates a complete individual with full energy.

Schools play a key role in providing the best personality development education to the learners. Teaching instruction, curriculum, and methods add to shaping the personality. The teachers motivate and establish interest in those activities which are helpful for the personality development of students. The personality of teachers, good ideas, positive attitude, and friendly behaviour encourage positive personality development. It is largely based on the interpersonal relationship of the teachers with the students in the schools. The value of respect, confidence, discipline, affection, creativity, honesty, ethics, self-evaluation, truthfulness and faithfulness are the core elements of personality development which are mainly accomplished in the schools. The school is the best

place for socialization. The students learned and understood the component of ethics and showed in the future. The school helps the students to develop their personality in every sense and enable to implement these experiences in every walk of life.

In Pakistan, public as well as private sector engage in delivering education at secondary level. Both sectors have different types of teaching and learning environment and also impart different types of knowledge relating to personality development and promotion of personality in the students. Therefore, the researcher was a concern to investigate the imparting of different aspects of personality development in both type of institutions and the experience of development of personality in the students. The statement of the problem was “A study of personality development of students at public and private schools of Punjab, Pakistan.”

The objective of the study

The major objective of this study was to compare the personality development of students in public and private schools of Punjab, Pakistan.

Research question

The research question of the study was to compare the personality development of students in public and private schools of Punjab, Pakistan.

Methods and Procedure of the Study

The research study was quantitative in nature and survey was conducted to collect data. All the teachers of secondary schools were the target population. There were total 88 (male 54 and female 34) public secondary schools in district Pakpattan. The total teachers were 1698 working in the public secondary schools. The researcher selected three (3) teachers from each public secondary school randomly. There was a total of 53 private schools working at the secondary level in district Pakpattan, and five teachers from each private school were selected on a random basis. Thus the sample was comprised of 264 teachers from the public schools and 265 teachers from private schools of Pakpattan. The two questionnaires were developed for the teachers. The first questionnaire was related to imparting knowledge of personality development provided by the schools while the second questionnaire was related to parameters of personality development promoted in the students. Both questionnaires were piloted and validated before data collection.

Review of the Related Literature

Cameron and Rychkak (1985) stressed the significance of infancy and early childhood. It describes the personality characters of the children and gives a picture of the inner life of human beings. The person speaks, respond, interaction with the community, gain experience and behavioral change. Self-determination theory emphasis on the social conditions of the individuals which lead to motivates natural process and psychological development. The components of the social condition are the characteristics of personality development like passive, proactive and engaged developed in the children. The three psychological needs are competence, autonomy and relatedness facilitate motivational level and health. The education, work, sports, and health are the domains of the psychological process (Rayan & Deci, 2000).

Blatt (2008) pointed out that “psychological development is a lifelong personal negotiation between two fundamental dimensions in human affairs and occurs from youth to old age as a synergistic interaction between anaclitic and introjective dimensions” According to Constantinople (1969) a significant difference was found between freshman and senior scores on industry, inferiority, and identity for both genders. The males showed a clear channel of increasing maturity over the four years as compared to females. International mobility is a life event influence on personality development includes in the socialization processes (Zimmermann, Julia & Franz, 2013).

Heaven, Lesson & Ciarrochi (2009) suggested that personality is not a static but a meaningful change. Personality development takes place during the adolescence period, and these personality traits are relevant to the school setting. According to John, Robins, and Pervin (2008), five factor theory is a contemporary explanation of trait theory based on the points that the people are knowable, rational, variable and proactive. Five factor theory described the operation of the universal personality system. The five personality factors are

neuroticism, extraversion, openness, agreeableness, and conscientiousness constitutes the main body of the personality system.

Neuroticism: The examples of neuroticism are depression, sadness, hopelessness, guilt, low self esteem, and pessimistic attitude.

Extraversion: The different words like gregariousness, social skills, numerous friendships, club memberships, participation in team sports and enterprising vocational interests are examples of the extraversion.

Openness to Experience: The meanings of openness are actions, novelty, interest in travel, hobbies, knowledge of foreign cuisine, the need of variety, diverse vocational interests and many friends of the same taste.

Agreeableness means compliance, forgiving attitude, belief in cooperation and inoffensive language.

Conscientiousness: High aspiration level, leadership skills, long term plans, organized support network, and technical expertise are the meanings of conscientiousness.

Tan and Hashim (2015) described that the personality difference was found between public and private institution male and female students. The students of public institution outscore in conscientiousness and neuroticism as compared to other components. The regression analysis shows that conscientiousness, neuroticism, and agreeableness significantly predicted of public and private institutional students. The male students outscored in openness and extraversion while the components like neurotic and agreeable were found in female students. The personality character was not ignored in an educational setting especially in the academic selection process.

Personality is the totality of ways, patterns of thoughts, feelings, and behaviour in which a person reacts and interacts with other persons. The psychological traits, characteristics, motives, beliefs, habits, attitudes and outlooks of individuals are included in the personality. The behavioural traits of infants and children are the personality modes include approach, activity, negative mode or fearfulness, anger, sociability, and persistence: sociability in a narrow sense and the traits like assertiveness, warmth, activity, sensation seeking, and positive emotions in a broad sense related to extraversion. Children select their own relationship and activities outside of the home and in fact as a function of their temperaments. Generally non shared the environment and events influence on neuroticism. It is the basic personality factor which is directly linked with clinical disorders, and it is the core of negative emotions like anxiety and depression. The psychoticism is the third major dimension of personality which includes conscientiousness, cautiousness, and socialization — the factors like sensation seeking, impulsivity and antisocial personality at one side and self-control at another side of psychoticism. The fourth dimension of personality is aggression is directly associated with emotional and attitudinal components like anger and hostility (Zuckerman, 2005).

According to Vivekananda (2009), personality is the way you behave, feel and think and it is the whole nature or character of a person. The person conducts himself in a given set of circumstances which is largely determined by the state of mind. The external appearance, mannerisms or speech are the real components of personality. Personality development refers to the deeper level of an individual, and therefore, it starts from a clear grasp of the nature of our mind and how it works and functions. Diaz Larenas, Rodriguez Moran and Poblete Rivera (2011) compared the teaching style and personality type. The public school respondents indicate facilitator teaching style with extrovert personality type while more authoritative teaching style with introvert personality type was found in the private school respondents. Nofle and Robins (2007) measure the relationship between a personality trait and academic outcomes. The relationship between openness and SAT verbal scores were independent of academic achievement and had mediating role concurrently as well as longitudinally through perceived verbal intelligence. The personality traits have independent and incremental effects on academic achievement. Poropat (2009) found that academic performance had significantly correlated with agreeableness, conscientiousness, and openness whereas conscientiousness and academic performance correlation was independent of intelligence. The interaction between different academic levels and age of respondents significantly moderated correlations with academic performance. The activities involve enhanced independence from family, success and failure in academic performance, beginning and endings of romantic

life, starting and achieving life objectives and goals and the start of the establishment of lifelong friendship — all these changing life activities along with the personality exhibit impressive levels of continuity. The level of continuity was not good, but most individuals' shows big changes in any one activity (Robins, Fraley, Roberts & Trzesniewski, 2001).

Roberts and Walton (2006) presented meta-analytic methods to express the channels of change in personality trait in the long life process. The individuals have enhanced socialism, conscientiousness, and emotional activity in the young 20 to 40 age group whereas measures of social vitality and openness increased in adolescence. The two factors like social and openness reduced in the old age group, but agreeableness also changed in old age.

Presentation and Analysis of Results

Table 1: Imparting Knowledge of Personality Development at Public and Private Secondary Schools

Sr. No	Measures of Personality Development	Mean		Standard Dev.		t	Sig.
		Public	Private	Public	Private		
1	Students' interaction with teachers	3.795	3.481	1.0225	1.1633	3.449	.001
2	Understanding the perks of learning things	3.424	3.148	1.0582	1.3040	2.805	.005
3	Regular workshop and seminars are conducted	3.492	3.250	1.0464	1.1056	2.581	.010
4	Sports activities perform as regular activities	3.295	2.750	1.0187	1.1821	5.264	.000
5	Mock interview sessions	3.428	3.061	1.0476	1.1354	4.101	.000
6	Guidance and counseling	3.489	3.398	.8763	1.1223	1.016	.311
7	Organizing cultural programs	3.455	3.572	1.1691	1.0440	-1.507	.133
8	Celebrating national and international festivals	3.375	3.519	1.0607	1.1892	-1.518	.130
9	Competition programs	3.364	3.420	1.2257	1.0101	-.624	.533
10	Learning disciplinary tasks	3.549	3.477	1.1054	1.0167	.739	.460
11	Clay modelling	3.314	3.341	.9610	.8574	-.355	.723
12	Activity based trainings	3.136	3.057	1.1910	.9946	.830	.407

N=264, $\alpha < .05$

The above table 1 reflects that there is a statistically significant difference between two groups of public and private schools for the first five parameters of imparting knowledge related to personality development. The value of t-statistics for the first five parameters are significant at $\alpha=0.05$. The mean score values ($X^- = 3.795$ & 3.481) for the first measure of imparting knowledge of personality development reflects that the student's interaction with teachers promotes in public schools as compared to the private schools. The mean score values ($X^- = 3.424$ & 3.148) for the second measure reveals that the understanding the perks of learning things seems good in public schools as compared to the private schools. The mean score values ($X^- = 3.492$ & 3.250) for the third measure shows that the workshop and seminars are conducted regularly in public schools as compared to private schools. The mean score values ($X^- = 3.295$ & 2.750) for the fourth measure of imparting knowledge reveals that the sports activities perform as regular activities in public schools as compared to the private schools. The mean score values ($X^- = 3.428$ & 3.061) for the fifth measure indicates that the more mock interview sessions conducted in public schools as compared to private schools.

The above table 1 reflects that there is no statistically significant difference between two groups of public and private schools for the last seven parameters of imparting knowledge regarding personality development. The value of t-statistics for last seven parameters are not significant at $\alpha=0.05$. The mean score values of parameters like guidance and counseling, disciplinary tasks learning and activity based training are promoting better in public schools as compared to private schools whereas, the parameters like organizing cultural programs, a celebration of national and international festivals, competition programs and clay modelling better in private schools as compared to public schools.

Table 2: Comparison of Personality Development of Students at Public and Private Secondary Schools

Sr. No	Parameters of Personality Development	Mean		Standard Dev.		t	Sig.
		Public	Private	Public	Private		
1	Self esteem	2.992	2.678	1.2177	1.2722	3.731	.000
2	Body language	3.121	2.871	1.1863	1.2109	3.080	.002
3	Creative problem solving	3.420	2.837	1.2430	1.1536	6.392	.000
4	Conflict and stress management	3.174	2.909	1.2083	1.2361	2.873	.004
5	Decision making skills	3.311	2.928	1.1545	1.1823	4.329	.000
6	Discipline	2.943	3.311	1.1895	1.1005	-4.008	.000
7	Character building	3.201	3.072	1.1673	1.1596	1.820	.070
8	Team work	3.235	3.095	1.1055	1.1007	1.920	.056
9	Time management	2.655	3.148	1.2900	1.1720	-5.493	.000
10	Respect religion diversity	3.148	2.932	1.2040	1.1349	2.645	.009
11	Good manners and etiquettes	3.261	3.042	1.2161	1.1379	2.617	.009
12	Participation in group discussion	3.216	3.144	1.3378	1.3319	.662	.509
13	Confidence	3.098	3.144	1.2169	1.2585	-.437	.663
14	Speaking skills	3.227	3.246	1.0898	1.2379	-.198	.843
15	Intellectual skills	3.193	3.239	1.1815	1.3167	-.454	.651
16	Attitude	2.811	2.981	1.2463	1.2500	-1.567	.118
17	Motivation	3.106	2.970	1.2100	1.0817	1.621	.106
18	Leadership qualities	3.163	3.068	1.1269	1.1483	1.205	.229
19	Respect cultural diversity	2.981	2.875	1.3466	1.2002	1.102	.271

N=264, $\alpha < .05$

The above table 2 reflects that there is a statistically significant difference between two groups of public and private schools for the first eleven parameters of personality development. The value of t-statistics for the first eleven parameters are significant at $\alpha=0.05$. The mean score values ($X^- = 2.992$ & 2.678) for the first measure of personality development reflects that the self-esteem of students developing better in public schools as compared to private schools. The mean score values ($X^- = 3.121$ & 2.871) for the second measure of personality development reveals that the body language of students seems good in public schools as compared to private schools. The mean score values ($X^- = 3.420$ & 2.837) for the third measure indicates that the problem solving creativity in students had given more value in public schools as compared to private schools. The mean score values ($X^- = 3.174$ & 2.909) for the fourth measure of personality development reveals that the conflict and stress manage in a better way in public schools as compared to the private schools. The mean score values ($X^- = 3.311$ & 2.928) for the fifth measure indicates that the decision making skills greater in students of public schools as compared to private schools. The mean score values ($X^- = 2.943$ & 3.311) for the sixth measure of personality development reflects that the discipline of students looks better in private schools as compared to public schools. The mean score values ($X^- = 3.201$ & 3.072) for the seventh measure of personality development reveals that the character building of students seems good in public schools as compared to the private schools. The mean score values ($X^- = 3.235$ & 3.095) for eight measure indicates that the objective of teamwork in students had given more value in public schools as compared to private schools. The mean score values ($X^- = 2.655$ & 3.148) for a ninth measure of personality development reveals that the time management for any task in a better way in private schools as compared to public schools. The mean score values ($X^- = 3.148$ & 2.932) for the tenth measure indicates that the respect regarding religious diversity greater in students of public schools as compared to private schools. The mean score values ($X^- = 3.261$ & 3.042) for the eleventh measure of personality development reflects that the manners and etiquettes look better in public schools as compared to the private schools.

The above table 2 reflects that there is no statistically significant difference between two groups of public and private schools for the last eight parameters of personality development. The value of t-statistics for last eight parameters are not significant at $\alpha=0.05$. The mean score values of parameters of personality development like participation in group discussion, motivational level, leadership qualities and respect of cultural diversity are developing better in public schools as compared to private schools while the parameters

like confidence, speaking skills, intellectual skills, and positive attitude promotes in private schools students as compared to public schools students.

Conclusion

The measures of personality development like students interaction with teachers, understanding the perks of learning things, workshop, seminars (assembly programs, the message of the day), sports activities and mock interview sessions are best conducted in public schools as compared to private schools. The personality development parameters like guidance and counseling, disciplinary tasks learning and activity based training are promoting better in public schools as compared to private schools whereas, the parameters like organizing cultural programs, a celebration of national and international festivals, competition programs and clay modelling better in private schools as compared to public schools.

The parameters of personality development such as self-esteem, body language, creative problem solving, conflict and stress management, decision making skills, character building, teamwork, respect religion diversity, good manners and etiquettes, participation in group discussion, motivation, leadership qualities and respect cultural diversity are well developed in students learning in public schools as compared to students learning in private schools. The parameters of personality development like discipline, time management, speaking skills, intellectual skills, confidence and attitude are best developed in students of private schools as compared to students of public schools.

Reference

- Ahmad, A. (2017). Role of teacher in student's personality development. *Psychology and Behavioral Science International Journal*, 2(2).
- Blatt, S. J. (2008). *Polarities of experience: Relatedness and self-definition in personality development, psychopathology, and the therapeutic process*. Washington, DC, US: American Psychological Association.
- Cameron, N., & Rychlak, J. F. (1985). *Personality development and psychopathology: A dynamic approach* (2nd ed.). Boston, MA, US: Houghton, Mifflin and Company.
- Constantinople, A. (1969). An Eriksonian measure of personality development in college students. *Developmental Psychology*, 1(4), 357-372.
- Diaz Larenas, C. H., Rodriguez Moran, A. V., & Poblete Rivera, K. J. (2011). Comparing teaching styles and personality types of EFL instructors in the public and private sectors. *Profile*, 13(1).
- Heaven, C. L. P., Lesson, P., & Ciarrochi, J. (2009). Personality development at school: Assessing a reciprocal influence model of teachers' evaluations and students' personality. *Journal of Research in Personality*, 43(2009).
- John, P. O., Robins, R. W., & Pervin, L. A. (2008). *Handbook of Personality: Theory and Research*, 3rd (ed). New York: The Guilford Press.
- Noftle, E. E., & Robins, R. W. (2007). Personality predictors of academic outcomes: Big five correlates of GPA and SAT scores. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 93(1).
- Poropat, A. E. (2009). A meta-analysis of the five-factor model of personality and academic performance. *Psychological Bulletin*, 135(2).
- Roberts, B. W., & Walton, K. E. (2006). Patterns of mean level change in personality traits across the life course: A meta-analysis of longitudinal studies. *Psychological Bulletin*, 132(1).
- Robins, R. W., Fraley, R. C., Roberts, B. W., & Trzesniewski, K. H. (2001). A longitudinal study of personality change in young adulthood. *Journal of Personality*, 69(4).
- Ryan, R. M., & Deci, E. L. (2000). Self-determination theory and the facilitation of intrinsic motivation, social development, and well-being. *American Psychologist*, 55(1).

Shukla, R. (2014). *Dictionary of Education*. New Delhi: A.P.H. Publishing Corporation.

Tan, C. S., & Hashim, I. H. M. (2015). Investigating personality differences between public and private university students and across gender: A focus on Malaysian Chinese sample. *International Journal of Development and Sustainability*, 4(2).

Vivekananda, S. (2009). *Personality Development*. India: Trio Press Kolkata.

Zimmermann., Julia, N., & Franz, J. (2013). Do we become a different person when hitting the road? Personality development of sojourners. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 105(3).

Zuckerman, M. (2005). *Psychobiology of Personality* 2nd ed. United Kingdom: Cambridge University Press.